

RESEARCH ARTICLE | OPEN ACCESS**Eradicating Extreme Poverty Amidst Covid-19 Pandemic: A Focus on Sub-Saharan Africa****Elias Igwebuike Agbo***Department of Accounting and Finance, Godfrey Okoye University, Ugwuomu-Nike, Emene, Enugu State, Nigeria****Corresponding Author: Agbo, E. I. | Godfrey Okoye University, Ugwuomu-Nike, Emene, Enugu State, Nigeria****Background**

Destitution is regarded universally as a serious issue that afflicts a significant percentage of the universe. It presents itself in diverse patterns like insufficiency of earnings and high-yielding resources as would guarantee maintainable means, persistent starvation and malnourishment, homelessness, absence of durable goods, disease, absence of clean water, deficiency of education, low life expectancy, etc (Ayoo,2022; Word Bank Development Report Report, 1990,2001; Sneyd,2015). Eliminating extreme poverty has been identified as an imperative as it possesses some dangerous consequences on the well-being of humanity (Ayoo,2022; Sachs, 2005). This is why removing it has been an important target in the MDGs embraced by the United Nations (UN) in the year 2000 (Ayoo, 2022). Though poverty exists universally, it is found to have been most prevalent in Sub-Sahara African (SSA) countries as well as those in Asia (Hamel, Tong, & Hofer ,2019). The causes of destitution in both regions are the implementation of policies that do not accommodate the interest of the destitute and which are biased against them, the absence of micro- enterprises and failures in governance. Even though past years have witnessed impressive individual country successes and speedy elimination of poverty globally, SSA is yet to tow that path. Growing population and slow speed of poverty elimination makes SSA the current center of abject poverty (World Bank, 2022; Liu, Feng, Wang, & Qiu, 2020; Liu et al.,2020; Beegle & Christiaensen,2019; Bapna,2012). SSA is regarded as a region that deserves serious attention for eliminating poverty, reason being that the population of the indigent in the region has kept on increasing, even when the rate of poverty is falling. Notwithstanding this abnormal situation in SSA, it appears that not much research has be carried out on this topic since the advent of COVID-19 using SSA as the focus. Consequently, this research has been undertaken to appraise the success achieved in unpacking the deprivation bundles of abject poverty amidst COVID-19, with SSA as its main focus. The remaining sections of this research have been organized thus: Literature review constitutes the second section. Section 3 contains the methodology. Section 4 highlights the menace of world-wide poverty and the progress being recorded in eradicating it. Section 5 explains the impact of COVID-19 on abject destitution in the Globe. Section 6 describes

ABSTRACT

For several decades before 2019, efforts were made by several organizations to lift many persons in the universe from abject poverty. Consequently, the level of extreme poverty declined steadily for a long period. However, this desire to bring poverty to an end started suffering significant setback from 2019 as soon big challenges like COVID-19 menace, violent conflicts and climate change took a center stage globally. Sub-Saharan Africa was found to be among the regions worst hit by the menace of penury. This work was intended to appraise the achievement made so far in eradicating indigence in Sub-Sahara Africa. Historical research approach was employed. It was realized that while a lot of gains have been made in the entire universe regarding the application of integrated strategies to minimize indigence, a significant part of the region is still swimming in abject poverty. This research recommends that efforts be intensified to regularly improve and update poverty data. In addition, integrated poverty alleviation strategies should not cease to be employed, particularly in SSA countries.

Keywords: *Poverty Reduction; Sub-Saharan Africa; Covid-19 Pandemic; Extreme Poverty*

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other issues militating against reducing poverty. Section 7 discusses future outlook of abject poverty while Section 8 contains the conclusion and recommendations.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Concept Extreme Poverty

Extreme poverty refers to a prolonged real-life experience of being incapable of affording basic meals, inability to send little ones to school, not having basic well-being maintenance and not possessing shelter above one's head (Kamruzzaman, 2021). It is probable to vary in different social, cultural, economic, and country contexts. Sen and Hulme (2006) posit that abject poverty be found quite often at the base of a communal pyramid frequently described as hardcore poor, ultra-poor, chronically poor, poorest as well as marginalized poor. For Oyen (2008), abject poverty will achieve the smallest on a mixture of variables that express fundamental states for personal life and existence.

International Poverty Line

International poverty line refers to a monetary threshold below which an individual is deemed to be poor. It is computed by employing the poverty threshold from each country after finding out the worth of the goods required to sustain one adult and converting it into dollars. The universal poverty thresholds were modernized in 2022, given the release of the Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) (World Bank Report, 2022). The current abject poverty line has become \$2.13 daily. It succeeds the poverty line of \$1.90 which was anchored on the PPP of 2017 (World Bank Report, 2022).

Causes of Poverty

Destitution or poverty has no single cause or single determinant. Instead, several complex factors drive poverty (Ajakaiye & Adeyeye, 2002). Some of its causes are low or negative growth in the economy, macroeconomic policies which are inappropriate, deficiencies in the market place which bring about limited job growth, abysmal productiveness and wages within the informal sector and a sluggish movement in development (Ajakaiye & Adeyeye, 2002).

Multidimensional Poverty Measure (MPM)

MPM is an indicator which shows the part of households in a nation that are denied along three aspects of well-being, namely monetary poverty, education and fundamental services (World Bank Report, 2022). Its computation takes into consideration numerous aspects of humanity over and above monetary poverty. Its purpose is to understand poverty over and above financial dispossessions. MPM got its inspiration from other prominent global multidimensional measure called Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI). The latter evolved through UNDP and Oxford University.

Challenges To Eliminating Extreme Poverty

Three major issues militate against eradicating abject poverty. They include the deepness of the poverty that continues to exist, the inconsistency in common well-being and the tenacious discrepancies in the non-income aspects of growth. (Cruz, Quillin, & Schellekens, 2015).

The Deepness of The Poverty

Poverty has remained very high and deep, particularly in SSA. The challenge is that even though poverty census rates provide information concerning the spatial spread of indigence and the degree of progress over time, it fails to make available a sufficient insight concerning significant disparities amid the extremely poor regarding the deepness of poverty.

The Inconsistency in Common Well-Being

There is an obvious disparity common well-being in addition to elimination abject destitution, the target of common well-being incorporates an essential goal of the World Bank (Cruz et al,2015). However, the occasional and delayed accessibility of family census data makes the appraisal of the global performance on general well-being difficult.

The Tenacious Discrepancies in the Non-Income Aspects of Development

There are discrepancies in the aspects of the “non-income” growth among the poor and the non-poor. The absolute hardships and inequalities of opportunities in these non-income aspects drive towards transferring poverty from one generation to another and destroying the speed and viability common well-being.

Theoretical Framework

Different groups of scholars have divergent perspectives concerning poverty (Davis & Sanchez-Martinez (2015). Over time, different schools of thought define poverty in manners that reflect some digressions from the monetary dimension to broader concerns like participation in politics and exclusion from the society. Bradly (2018) categorizes majority of poverty theories into three families. Davis and Sanchez-Martinez (2015) summarize the economic theories of poverty as;

The Classical and Neoclassical Theories

These theories claim that human beings are ultimately accountable for being poor. The classical theory proposes that the outcomes of the give-and-take going on in the market place are efficient. As such, wages paid to individuals perfectly reflect their productivity. Thus, the wrong choices made by individuals may lead them into poverty net. Neoclassical economics recognizes more embracing causes of indigence which surpass the control of individuals (particularly, market failures). Both classical and neoclassical theories lay emphasize much on financial aspects and on the part played by the individual person, as opposed to the group, in creating poverty. They claim that government has a limited role in eradicating poverty.

Keynesian/Neoliberal Theory

This school of thought is more concerned with the forces of macro-economy. The proponents of this theory lay emphasis on the responsibility of government to stabilize the economy and provide public goods. They consider poverty to be mainly involuntary and as created by lack of employment opportunities

Marxian Theory

This poverty theory considers discrimination among classes and groups as the major causes of indigence. It assigns an essential role to the government in regulating the market place.

Social Exclusion and Social Capital Theories

These theories recognize the part played by both social and economic factors in creating poverty. Those factors help in comprehending the forerunners of poverty and its persistence over time. This work is anchored on both the Marxian and Keynesian theories as both of them propose that government has a significant responsibility in stabilizing the economy, providing public goods and eradicating poverty.

Empirical Review

Barrientos, Hulme and Shepherd (2005). sought to determine whether social is capable of tackling chronic poverty. They observed that attention regarding social security had moved towards risk and susceptibility They discovered that just as developments in social security cause indigency directly, they also cause it indirectly through the manner that poor households react to risks. In addition, they noticed that the degree to which social security mediations can address constant indigence is not clear. After discussing these issues, the study concluded that elaborate social security is capable of persistently poor. Deaton (2005) researched on measuring indigence in a growing world. Deaton noticed that the degree to which development has been a subject of dispute for thirty years. He discovered

that, even with better and more and reliable data available presently, the controversies have not been resolved.

Oyen (2008) strived to find out why indigence was not being focused on It contended that to eliminate indigence, there has to be relevant, reliable and research-based knowledge. The author considered it paradoxical that three out of the most important models in the research concerning poverty have not focused their attentions on abject poverty directly. Bruton, Ketchen and Ireland (2013) researched on how poverty can be eradicated through entrepreneurship. The authors discovered that the individuals living in penury should not be considered as a merchandise. Rather, comprehending how to assist the poor in creating their own businesses is where the solution lies. They concluded that entrepreneurship among the poor will ultimately bring an enduring solution to their indigence. Hermes (2014) addressed the question on whether the participation of the poor individuals in micro-finance can help in minimizing a country's extent of inequality. in income. With the details obtained from seventy developing nations, Hermes established that increased levels of microfinance involvement are connected with the reduction of income gap among the rich and the poor. However, it was found that the effects of microfinance in minimizing unevenness in income are not much.

Bicaba, Brixiová and Ncube (2015) strived to determine the trends and policies regarding the eradication of abject poverty in Africa and the played by international organizations. The authors noticed that eliminating poverty for everybody everywhere universally by the year 2030 was goal number 1 among the Sustainable Development goals of the United Nations. They summarized several articles on eliminating poverty universally and examined the of achieving this target for SSA. They found that, under credible assumptions, abject poverty would not be eradicated in SSA by 2030 but could be reduced to low levels. McCoy (2017) challenged the mainstream narratives that claim satisfactory advancement in the efforts made to minimize indigence and ameliorate health for all. McCoy argued that the elimination of poverty which is consistent with environmental sustainability will require laying emphasis more explicitly concerning the redistribution of competence and wealth. He opined that the health community in the world has been significantly socialized into believing that advancement and solutions in the future can secured from more socialistic growth, advancement in technology and philanthropic endeavor. Page and Pande (2018) strived to know why money is not enough to terminate world-wide penury. The study observed that the proportion of the world community living in abject poverty had dropped by thirty-four per cent. The reason adduced was that such speedy decrease would be continuously difficult to obtain because:

- I. Most of the poor reside in the countries with middle income where the gains arising from development haven been shared discriminatorily and unequally often and
- II. A huge collection of abject poverty continues to be found in low-income nations where development is erratic and monetary assistance often does not extend to the poor.

Hanna and Olken (2018) studied anti-poverty programs in less developed nations They recognized that the first among the seventeen MDGs set by the UN is the elimination of extreme poverty by the year 2030. They observed that, while future growth of the economy might continue to reduce poverty, it would not arrest the issue by itself. In addition, the study noticed the existence of a potentially significant part to be played by national-level transfer programs which help poor families in developing nations and that those kinds of programs are often run by developing country governments. Jafino, Walsh, Rozenberg and Hallegatte (2020) reviewed the estimates of the effects of climate change on indigence by2030. Thousands of storylines were employed to make available the update. The study established that the estimate the population of the persons entering destitution as a result of climate change were more than thirty-two million in most scenarios. Health effects were found to be responsible for the greater aspect while health effects, natural disasters, and food prices were critical in South Asia. Hotez, Fenwick and Molyneux (2021) examined the recent COVD-19 poor as well as the resurrection of the abandoned tropical illnesses. They noticed that over one hundred million persons were pushed back to abject poverty due to COVID-19. Kamruzzaman (2021) strived to comprehend the meaning of extreme poverty having the poor in Bangladesh in perspective. The study discovered that, from the perspective of Bangladesh, comparing the experiences of the adjudged poor and the present definition of based on dollar-based definition of extreme poverty appears to show varying images. It noticed that should the perceptions of the poor differ significantly from the current yardstick, poverty elimination in the world development enterprise might turn into a mere statistical achievement. The study concluded that reducing poverty can be achieved by stimulating the growth of the economy in order to beef up incomes and increase employment opportunities for poor people Ayoo (2022) considers the presence of abject poverty in many developing nations as an important issue that needs to be tackled urgently because of its negative implications on human well-being. Ayoo asserts that poverty eradication can be achieved by stimulating economic growth.

Methodology

This research aligns with Parker (1997) and Peace (2021) in employing the historical research design. The data for it were sourced from several documents and synthesized. Previous occurrences were employed to arrive at conclusions and make forecasts concerning the future. The reason for employing the historical research approach was to enable one to obtain every factual proof basis for answering the research questions (Snyder, 2019). Clear and systematic approaches were used while reviewing the related articles so as to avoid bias. Also, the essence was to obtain the results which are reliable enough for making valid conclusions (Moher, Liberati, Tetzlaff & Altman, 2010).

The Level of Extreme Poverty and The Progress Being Made in Eradicating It

Despite all the efforts put in by international agencies to eliminate extreme poverty, it became more widespread in several countries in the past ten years more than before (OECD, 2022). This made poverty eradication the major departmental issue in the 21st century. By 2015, 189 countries took part in the Millennium Declaration to eliminate extreme poverty. At least 25 international agencies and non-governmental organizations were involved in making frantic attempt to bring poverty to an end (Human Rights Career, 2022). World Bank Report (2022) asserts that indigence has been on the decline globally. However, the rate of its decline was reduced by the economic impacts of COVI-19 pandemic which was reported to have dragged no less than 100 million persons into abject poverty Human Right Careers (2022) affirms that World Social Summit considered poverty eradication as an imperative of humanity and urged public authorities of nations to tackle the fundamental causes of poverty, provide the fundamental requirements of everybody and make sure that the indigent have access to productive assets like credit, education and training. In recognition of insufficient advancement in alleviating poverty, it was decided in the 24th special session of the General Assembly to have a second look at the Copenhagen Commitments. The General Assembly resolved to set up targets to cut down the percentage of humans living in abject poverty by fifty percent in 2015. This target was endorsed by the Summit as MDG 1. The Second UN Decade for the Eradication of Poverty 2008-2017) proclaimed by the General Assembly in December 2007, was intended to support a broad framework for poverty eradication. It put much emphasis on the necessity to strengthen the role of the UN as a leader in encouraging international cooperation for development, critical for the eradication of poverty (Human Right Careers (2022).

Progress Recorded Globally in Eradicating Extreme Poverty

The focus of SDG target has been to eliminate extreme poverty by 2030. In 2015 when the SDGs were adopted, the target appeared ambitious but within reach. As the global population increased, the people in extreme poverty reduced (World Bank Report, 2022). World Bank Report (2022) discloses that the world population rose 5.3 to 7.5 billion between 1993 and 2017. However, during the same period, the population of the people living in extreme poverty dropped from 1.9 billion to 689 million. However, there was unequal spread of poverty among the nations and regions. From the early 1990s, abject poverty prevailed globally in excess of 30 percent. However, this thirty percent average covered great differences among the countries. For instance, some of them in Europe and North America had virtually no record of extreme poverty while several countries in SSA, East Asia and South Asia had extreme poverty rate in excess of 70 percent. Out of 1.2 billion persons that did not suffer extreme poverty between 1993 and 2017, eighty percent of them were in China and India. China reduced its abject poverty rate from 57 percent in 1993 to lower than 1 percent in the most recent year that household survey was carried out. India reduced its extreme poverty rate by fifty percent between 1993 and 2011. Its 2017 extreme poverty rate was expected to be slightly above the global average 9.2 percent. Since 2011, World Bank Report (2022) indicates that the decrease in extreme poverty since 1993 –from 1.9 billion to 689 million- persons in 27 years- remained a very great achievement. World Bank Report (2022) discloses that more than 136 million persons were living below the international poverty line in 2015. Approximately ten percent of the global population (pre-pandemic) was living in abject poverty and striving to acquire the most basic necessities like health, education, etc. For everyone hundred men of the same age group, one hundred and twenty-two women aged between twenty-five and thirty-four would be expected to live in penury, while over 160 million children would be at risk of continuing to be trapped in abject poverty by 2030. The report added that Southern Asia and SSA were expected to notice the largest boost in indigence. They would have additional thirty-two million and twenty-six million persons respectively living below the international poverty line due to COVID-19. According to World Bank Report (2022), the proportion of the universe living in abject poverty went down by fifty percent in the previous decade. It dropped from 14.3 percent in 2010 to 7.1 percent in 2019. In 2016, 55 percent of the global population- approximately four billion persons - did not benefit from any form of

social security. From 2015 to 2018, global destitution continued its historical decline. The global poverty rate plummeted from 10.1 percent in 2015 to 8.6 percent in 2018. Owing to the menace of COVID-19, the global poverty rate rose sharply from 8.3 percent in 2019 to 9.2 percent in 2020.

Extreme Poverty in SSA

In SSA, abject poverty declined (World Bank, 2022). It decreased from approximately sixty percent in 1993 to about forty percent in 2017. However, because of speedy population growth, the number of persons living in penury moved up from 335 million to 431 million. The highest number of the extremely poor are centralized in SSA (World Bank Report, 2022). This concentration of penury has drifted from Asia to Africa. At present, astronomical population growth coupled with stubbornly high abject poverty rates in SSA has become the dominant force determining global poverty (World Bank Report, 2022). In SSA, the number of persons trapped in extreme poverty has risen. World Bank reports that eight among the ten nations having the highest number of the extremely poor are in SSA. The countries include Nigeria, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Tanzania, Madagascar, Mozambique, Kenya and Uganda.

Impact of Covid-19 On Extreme Poverty in the Universe

No one can say with certainty to what degree COVID-19 has affected extreme poverty in the entire universe (Kharas, 2020). Kharas explains that the data on poverty are usually obtained from the surveys of households. Consequently, for obvious reasons, it is impossible to conduct proper surveys under current conditions in several countries. That notwithstanding it is common knowledge that economic growth is the strongest driver of destitution. ((Kharas, 2020). For this indicator, the IMF has just produced recent estimates in respect of 2020 and beyond. One can make inferences with regard to the effect of COVID-19 on poverty. Before the advent of COVID-19, baseline estimates had submitted that six percent of the world population might still be trapped in extreme poverty in 2030. This would entail failing to achieve the goal of eliminating destitution. All over the world, there was a widespread rise in extreme poverty from 2020. For the first time in twenty years the global portion of workers that live with their families below the international poverty line moved up from 6.7 percent in 2019 to 7.2 percent in 2020. This was occasioned by the COVID-19 menace which still remains (Mahler, Yonzan, Lakner, Aguilar & Wu, 2021). Mahler, et al. (2021) affirms that the COVID-19 induced poor in the year 2021 has continued to remain at 97 million persons. United Nations (2022) reports that, generally, the action to achieve the SDGs is not yet progressing at the speed or scale required by 2030. United Nations (2022) observes that prior to the COVID-19 issue, reasonable advancement was being made in eliminating poverty in several nations within Eastern and Southeastern Asia. The COVID-19 pandemic was feared to be capable of moving between 88 million to 115 million persons into abject poverty in 2020. There was likely to be a total increase of this to as many as 150 million by 2021, depending on the severity of the contraction of the economy. As a result of the menace of COVID-19 palaver, the world-wide poverty rate rose speedily from 8.3 percent in 2019 to 9.2 percent in 2020. This represented the initial rise in extreme poverty since 1990 and a set-back of poverty reduction by approximately three years. United Nations (2022) contends that the effect of COVID-19 issue reversed the steady progress of poverty decrease over the past 25 years. The rising inflation and the effect of the war in Ukraine are reported to have further worsened the situation. United Nations (2022)'s forecast was that these combined crises would drag an additional 75 to 95 million persons into extreme poverty in 2022. The problem emanating from COVID-19 had threatened to push more than 70 million persons into penury.

Intervention by World Bank Group

As soon as COVID-19 set in, the World Bank Group took broad and quick steps to assist developing nations in strengthening their pandemic response (World Bank (2022)). They supported the interventions of public health by striving to ensure that key supplies and equipment flow perfectly, assisting the private sector to continue to function properly as sustaining jobs. They deployed no less than \$160 billion as financial assistance for more than fifteen months so as to empower more than 100 nations to protect the poor and vulnerable. According to World Bank (2022), this included \$50 billion as grants and very concessional loans to the poor.

Other Issues Militating Against Poverty Alleviation in the SSA

Climate Change

Climate change is an important issue that militates against poverty reduction. It pushes up food insecurity, poverty as well as displacement. In SSA, insecurity of food rises by between 5 and 10 percent with each flood or drought. According to World Meteorological Organization (WMO), the complicated impact of protracted conflicts, political instability, climate variability, pest outbreaks and economic crises, worsened by costs of adjusting to climate change to avoid even higher costs of additional disaster relief, were estimated by WMO at US\$ 30–50 billion each year in the coming decade.

Efforts by Philanthropic Organizations to End Poverty in SSA

SSA has countries that possess different geographies, histories, cultures and needs. The issues they face range from unaffordable health care to regional conflict. Those issues have left many inhabitants of SSA in poverty. Philanthropic organizations have tasked themselves to remedy the several challenges affecting sub-Saharan Africa (Portner2022). Numerous charitable entities work on tackling poverty in SSA. Prominent among them are three bodies that have demonstrated that single universal approach exists for tackling poverty in SSA, namely Nanmo, Efficiency for Access and Zoetis (Portner2022). Nanmo is a partnership formed by Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation and the Qatar Fund for Development in Africa. It has the objective of providing adaptive ways for local farmers, especially women, for responding to climate-related difficulties. Nanmo gives agrarian communities innovative technologies which is capable of supporting their routes to food security. In SSA, over 600 million persons are not connected to the grid of their country. Efficiency for Access is a coalition coordinated by CLASP and Energy Saving Trust, works to bring life-changing, clean-energy appliances to vulnerable communities. It is concerned with closing the gap between those persons that are on and off the energy grid in the SSA. This is expected to bring about some improvement in agricultural productivity and thus poverty alleviation. In addition to agricultural appliances like solar water pumps. This non-governmental organization also supplies products like solar-powered refrigerators, electric pressure cookers and fans. Zoetis provides veterinary assistance to the livestock of farmers. Sub-Saharan Africa possesses a large livestock population. Even though Africa has large livestock population, it has the lowest degree of productivity per animal among other regions. Zoetis improves the health of livestock through its ALPHA Initiative. This program provides accessible veterinary services to farmers throughout the SSA region. By supplying inoculations and medical training to communities in SSA, the ALPHA has boon for food security in SSA. Zoetis's activity in this region has enabled African communities to produce safer food while reducing the economic problem of raising livestock.

Civil Conflicts

Escalation of civil conflict is a significant issue that influences poverty movements in SSA. The statistics of conflicts went up from 6 in 1980 to 10 in 1999. In 1999 alone, at least 15 countries experienced vigorous armed dispute in SSA. Almost all of them were internationalized including state actors (whether directly or through proxies), the transnational activities of brutal Islamist groups, other armed groups and criminal networks. One of the brutal conflicts that enhance extreme poverty in SSA is the Russia-Ukraine war. Russia is an important supplier of fertilizer. The conflict between Russia and Ukraine affects the cost incurred in exporting fertilizer from Russia. As SSA depends on fertilizer importation from Russia, it buys them bought at very huge amounts and, consequently, their usage in the region is low. Because of low quantity usage of fertilizers, poor soil quality and the absence of advanced technology, crop yields are reduced and incomes are low in the SSA countries. Hence, the Russia-Ukraine war increases turmoil in SSA (Pinto, 2022).

The Future Prospect of Extreme Poverty Eradication

The projections made that destitution would be eradicated by 2030 is not likely to materialize. Prior to the advent of COVID -19, the global poverty rate was expected to continue to fall to around 8 percent in January 2020. Under more pessimistic assumptions, over 100 million persons are feared to have entered abject poverty. World Bank advise that even though predicting how poverty would trend in any particular country is impossible, abject poverty is likely to continue existing in several nations even beyond 2030 unless dramatic accelerations are made to reduce poverty. While most of the extreme poverty rates rise in some countries, SSA has the largest share -five out of seven. These include some of the poorest countries in the globe like Madagascar, Angola, and Liberia. For the nations in SSA, extreme poverty is likely to be eradicated in 2040. The current trends show that abject poverty is likely to linger

for decades in some countries.

Conclusion

The study appraised the advance made so far globally in eliminating abject poverty, particularly in SSA. It employed the historical research approach. The study observed that success has been made across the universe regarding the employment of integrated poverty curtailment strategies. All the same, it found that 1.2 million persons in 111 developing nations are still extremely poor. In addition, it noticed that SSA faces some challenges which may make it incapable of eliminating abject poverty by the target year and that it can only bring it to low levels by 2030.

Recommendations

The paper makes the following recommendations: -

1. National and regional strategies in Sub-Saharan Africa should target at some growth which is strong, inclusive, resilient to shocks and of better and higher quality. This will enable them to succeed in reducing poverty substantially.
2. Efforts should be resumed to regularly improve on and update poverty and integrated data.
3. Poverty curtailment strategies should continue to be employed most particularly in the poverty-stricken nations as well as the places of residence of the very poor persons.
4. International agencies should play more important part in encouraging the coordination of policies aimed at eliminating poverty globally.
5. Governments of developed countries and international agencies should be more active in bringing the perspectives of SSA into universal economic debates on those matters that affect continuous development on the continent.
6. To tackle abject poverty, policymakers in SSA and development partners should anticipate drivers of change in the long term.
7. It is advisable for SSA countries to adapt to climate change and integrate responses to it.
8. SSA countries should extend their poverty elimination agenda beyond the MDGs; the focus should be on wealth creation and prosperity as well as inequality reduction.

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